

Information, Shannon's Entropy and Violating Initial Constraints

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One may maximize Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i f(e_i) = 1$ where $f(e_i)$ is the probability to have a gas particle with energy e_i . This yields $f(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ from which one may calculate E_{ave} . The result, however, is consistent with a canonical distribution, not a microcanonical one for which total energy = E_{ave} is a strict constraint. For the canonical approach one considers weights $\exp(-E_i/T)$ where E_i may be larger than E_{ave} . (E_i is the sum of e_i 's.) In other words, one violates the original microcanonical constraint on total energy (for ease of calculation). This is consistent with Shannon's entropy for which "information" is $-\ln(f(e_i))$. If one thinks in terms of two body elastic scattering then $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. One may use any e_1 and e_2 even if their sum is greater than E_{ave} the microcanonical constraint. Thus the use of information or Shannon's entropy may violate original constraints in a problem.

In this note we wish to examine an example (1) from information theory involving the compression of bits used to represent six letters A-F which have different probabilities of occurrence. Six letters may be encoded using $2 \times 2 \times 2$ bits. This is an initial kind of constraint or bound i.e. one needs 3 bits for each letter. Given the probabilities one may calculate $-\ln(\text{probability}) = \text{information}$ of each letter which represents the number of bits needed for each. The idea of information as $-\ln(\text{probability})$ is part of Shannon's entropy. The problem is that like in the case of the canonical distribution violating the microcanonical constraint on total energy = E_{ave} (which is done for ease of calculation), using information may violate an existing constraint or bound already in the problem. For example, for a low probability, $-\ln(\text{probability})$ may be larger than 3 the original bound or constraint used for the uniqueness of 6 letters. Using Shannon-Fano coding, a letter is coded with a number of bits close to $-\ln(\text{probability})$ which means that for $-\ln(\text{probability}) > 3$, the number of bits needed is larger than the original bound or constraint. The idea, however, in information theory is to compress the number of bits. Furthermore there is no "ease of calculation" as in the case of the canonical distribution. We investigate this idea in this note.

Shannon's Information And Two-Body Scattering

Consider an ideal gas with two body elastic scattering. For equilibrium one may suggest a time reversal balance exists for each reaction i.e.

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

Taking $-\ln$ of the latter leads to $-\ln(f(e_1)) + -\ln(f(e_2)) = -\ln(f(e_3)) + -\ln(f(e_4))$ suggesting that $-\ln(f(e_1))$ (unnormalized) is proportional to e_1 . In fact, $f(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ where T is a parameter. Thus $-\ln(f(e_i))$ where $f(e_i)$ is the probability to have a particle with e_i appears as "information" and is proportional to e_i . An issue with ((1)), however, is that it does not include any cutoff on energies. For a microcanonical distribution the total energy is fixed. In ((1)) one may choose e_i values larger than the total energy which is a violation of this constraint. This is equivalent to

considering $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ as being the same as the E_{total} microcanonical constraint. In other words one uses a canonical distribution linked with $\exp(-E_i/T)$ which is sharply peaked and approximately describes a microcanonical scenario with its exact energy constraint. If E_i can take on any value, single particle e_i may as well although this may violate the exact energy microcanonical constraint. Thus using $\ln(f(e_i))$ as information may yield values which are higher than initial bounds or constraints. In the case of the canonical distribution, one relaxes the strict constraint on total energy for ease of calculation. The idea is that the canonical distribution closely approximates the microcanonical one even though one allows for e_i values which violate constraints. Dropping constraints makes the calculation much easier.

Information Theory

We next consider the example provided in (1). Consider six letters A-F which have probabilities: .3, .1, .02, .15, .4, .03. In order to use bits (0 or 1) to encode these letters uniquely one may consider $2 \times 2 \times 2$ as being more than sufficient. In such a case, each letter is uniquely described by 3 bits. For example, A may be described by 000 etc. This is an initial bound or constraint in the problem.

Next we consider the idea of information i.e. $\ln(\text{probability})$. Unlike the case of a classical gas for which one tries to calculate probabilities by maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint, in the information theory example, like for a coin or die, the probabilities are given. One may, however, calculate information = $\ln(\text{probability})$ for each letter and like in the gas case information is like a quantity e.g. energy. Furthermore, $\ln(\text{probability})$ may violate original bounds or constraints just like in the gas case where it was linked to a canonical theory when actually a microcanonical one applies. As a result, if $\ln(\text{probability}) > 3$, one violates the original bound or constraint of 3. In the example of (1), this occurs for letters B probability = .1 information = 3.32, F probability .03 information 5.06 and C probability .02 information 5.64.

Using Shannon-Fano coding (presented in (1)) one maps the letters into a number of bits roughly equal to the information value. In particular, B is mapped into 4 bits and F and C into 5 each. These values, however, violate the original bound or constraint of 3 bits per letter. The object is to compress information and so it is surprising that the initial constraint or bound of 3 would be violated as this is the opposite of compression. Thus one sees that using information may violate original constraints or bounds.

The average information or Shannon's entropy: $\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$ equals 2.057 bits/letter as shown in (1) so this is better than the original 3 bits per letter scheme. As a result, using information ($\ln(\text{probability})$) leads to compression (as shown by Shannon's entropy) even though one may violate original bounds or constraints for particular letters (i.e. low probability ones). This is analogous to the canonical gas with $f(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$. High e_i values which violate energy constraints lead to low $f(e_i)$ i.e. probability.. In particular instead of using 4 bits for B and 5 for F and C each, one could use the original bound of 3 and obtain more compression. Unlike the canonical distribution for a gas, there are no ease of calculation gains in this example. Information $\ln(\text{probability})$ for low probabilities leads to values which are greater than the original bound or constraint.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the idea of information $\ln(\text{probability})$ appears in an ideal gas described by a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $f(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ where T is temperature and e_i the energy of a particle. $\ln(f(e_i))$ is linked with e_i , a physical quantity, which is conserved in elastic scattering. In fact, one may obtain the idea of information by considering equilibrium as a situation for which there is a balance of reaction and its time reversed reaction. Assuming that the probability for e_1 and e_2 to scatter is the product of their probabilities:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \text{ and } f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$$

Taking \ln of the latter leads to $f(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$. A problem is that if one treats the case in a microcanonical manner i.e. there is a fixed total energy E_{ave} , one sees there is no constraint on e_1 etc. In other words one may have an e_i greater than E_{ave} . As a result, one uses a canonical distribution approach such that $E_{\text{ave}} = \sum_i E_i \exp(-E_i/T)$ or at the single particle level: $E_{\text{ave}}/N = \sum_i e_i \exp(-e_i/T)$. Here N is the number of particles. In both cases, E_i or e_i take on all possible values i.e. even values greater than E_{ave} the total energy. Thus the idea of information $\ln(\text{probability})$ is associated with the possible violation of initial constraints or bounds.

We consider an example from information theory described in (1). One has 6 letters A-F and uses 3 bits to describe each uniquely. This is an initial bound or constraint. Next one uses the idea of information $\ln(\text{probability})$ to find the information of each letter. Probabilities for each are supplied in (1). This issue is that $\ln(\text{probability}) > 3$ for three letters meaning information violates initial constraints/bounds. In particular in (1) a Shannon-Fano coding approach is used which assigns roughly $\ln(\text{probability})$ bits to each letter in order to create compression.

If one calculates the average information i.e. Shannon's entropy, this value is less than 3 so on average there is compression, but initial bounds or constraints are violated for 3 letters. In particular one letter is encoded with 4 bits and two others with 5. The small probabilities (which lead to $\ln(\text{probability}) > 3$) mean the letters do not show up often in messages, but one could nevertheless have retained the original scheme (bound or constraint) of 3 bits for them and obtained more compression.

Unlike the canonical distribution for a gas where one violates the total energy constraint for ease of calculation, there is no reduction in the ease of calculation by using large $\ln(\text{probability})$ numbers of bits which violate the original bound or constraint.

In (1) it is noted that these large (>3) encodings are a disadvantage and a different method of encoding is presented which yields better compression. In this note, we wish to argue that the idea of $\ln(\text{information})$ in both physics (classical gas) and information theory (encoding of message) may violate initial bounds or constraints. $\ln(\text{probability})$ arise from (A) $\ln(\text{probability}_1 * \text{probability}_2) = \ln(\text{probability}_1) + \ln(\text{probability}_2)$ i.e. it acts like a quantity, but there may be original bounds on this quantity. For example, for a gas the quantity is e_i (energy) which is bounded under a microcanonical constraint and in information theory it is the number of bits needed for the letter with probability (i) which may have an original bound which is to be improved upon for compression. These constraints/bounds are not incorporated into the scheme (A) i.e. into the idea of information.

References

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